

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/368302797>

Negrea–Muraru consecutive prime numbers relation, and adjacent Negrea–Muraru Conjecture Babeş–Bolyai University

Experiment Findings · February 2023

DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23746.86721

CITATIONS

0

READS

78

2 authors, including:

Negrea Petru-Cristian
Babeş-Bolyai University

2 PUBLICATIONS 0 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Some of the authors of this publication are also working on these related projects:

Negrea-Muraru consecutive prime numbers relation, and adjacent Negrea-Muraru Conjecture [View project](#)

Negrea-Muraru consecutive prime numbers relation, and adjacent Negrea-Muraru Conjecture

Babeş-Bolyai University

Authors

Negrea Petru-Cristian

Muraru Marian-Laurențiu

Romania, Cluj

February 2023

Summary

§ Section 1 (Consideration and novel symbol)

§ Section 2 (Research – Application of consideration; encompassing results; observations)

§ Section 3 (Algebraic Method – Proof of interval of $\mathbb{R}$)

§ Section 4 (Conjecture)

§ Section 1 (Consideration and novel symbol)

I. Consideration

Consider the sequence of all positive prime numbers:

2, 3, 5, 7, 11, 13, 17, 19, 23, 29, 31, 37, 41, 43, 47, 53, 59, 61, 67, 71, 73, 79, 83, 89, 97, ... ∞

Let a, b be consecutive prime numbers, $a > b$ such that:

$$\frac{a}{b} + \frac{b}{a} = R_{(a,b)} = R$$

II. Novel symbol

For future representative and structural purposes, a quantitative symbol is to be established.

Proposed symbol:

- $\equiv$

Definition:

- the symbol $\equiv$ represents the remaining results or values of a properly delimited group, arrangement or series encompassing all results or values of said group, arrangement or series.

Usage:

- it is used to mention, observe or present a relation between one or more extracted results or values of a properly delimited group, arrangement or series encompassing all results or values of said group, arrangement or series, and all the other results or values of the properly delimited group, arrangement or series.

Example:

- Group A contains the elements {1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9}
- $\therefore$ by definition $1 < 2 < 3 < 4 < 5 < 6 < 7 < 8 < 9 \therefore 1 < \equiv$ elements of Group A

Therefore, consider the following symbol $\equiv$ to denote "all other".

§ Section 2 (Research – Application of consideration; encompassing results; observations)

I. Application of consideration

2, 3, 5, 7, 11, 13, 17, 19, 23, 29, 31, 37, 41, 43, 47, 53, 59, 61, 67, 71, 73, 79, 83, 89, 97, ... ∞

a, b are consecutive p numbers

$a > b$

$$\frac{a}{b} + \frac{b}{a} = R_{(a,b)} = R$$

$$\frac{3}{2} + \frac{2}{3} = R_{(3,2)} = 2.1(6)$$

$$\frac{5}{3} + \frac{3}{5} = R_{(5,3)} = 2.2(6)$$

II. Encompassing results

$$R_{(7,5)} = 2.1142857143...$$

$$R_{(11,7)} = 2.2077922078...$$

$$R_{(13,11)} = 2.027972028$$

$$R_{(17,13)} = 2.07239819$$

$$R_{(19,17)} = 2.0123839009...$$

$$R_{(23,19)} = 2.0366132723...$$

$$R_{(29,23)} = 2.0539730135...$$

$$R_{(31,29)} = 2.0044493882...$$

$$R_{(37,31)} = 2.0313862249...$$

$$R_{(41,37)} = 2.0105471325...$$

$$R_{(43,41)} = 2.0022688599...$$

$$R_{(47,43)} = 2.0079168728...$$

$$R_{(53,47)} = 2.0144520273...$$

$$R_{(59,53)} = 2.0115126319...$$

$R_{(61,59)} = 2.0011114198\dots$
 $R_{(67,61)} = 2.0088084169\dots$
 $R_{(71,67)} = 2.0033634644\dots$
 $R_{(73,71)} = 2.0007717538\dots$
 $R_{(79,73)} = 2.0062424137\dots$
 $R_{(83,79)} = 2.0024401403\dots$
 $R_{(89,83)} = 2.0048734263\dots$
 $R_{(97,89)} = 2.0074134136\dots$
 $R_{(101,97)} = 2.001633153$
 $R_{(103,101)} = 2.0003845045\dots$
 $R_{(107,103)} = 2.0014517739\dots$
 $R_{(109,107)} = 2.0003429649\dots$
 $R_{(113,109)} = 2.0012990176\dots$
 $R_{(127,113)} = 2.0136575848\dots$
 $R_{(131,127)} = 2.0009617118\dots$
 $R_{(137,131)} = 2.0020059063\dots$
 $R_{(139,137)} = 2.0002100509\dots$
 $R_{(149,139)} = 2.0048283521\dots$
 $R_{(151,149)} = 2.0001777857\dots$
 $R_{(157,151)} = 2.0015185388\dots$
 $R_{(163,157)} = 2.0014067446\dots$
 $R_{(167,163)} = 2.0005877815\dots$
 $R_{(173,167)} = 2.0012460628\dots$
 $R_{(179,173)} = 2.0011625279\dots$
 $R_{(181,179)} = 2.0001234606\dots$
 $R_{(191,181)} = 2.0028925978\dots$

- 4-digits consecutive p:

$$R_{(5471,5449)} = 2.00001623535685700128...$$

- 5-digits consecutive p:

$$R_{(25579,25577)} = 2.00000000611401959013$$

- 6-digits consecutive p:

$$R_{(999233,999221)} = 2.0000000001442228824...$$

- 7-digits consecutive p:

$$R_{(4817381,4817357)} = 2.00000000002482005023...$$

- 8-digits consecutive p:

$$R_{(64944221,64944211)} = 2.00000000000002370931...$$

- 9-digits consecutive p:

$$R_{(984972719,984972697)} = 2.00000000000000049887...$$

- 10-digits consecutive p:

$$R_{(8614259561,8614259551)} = 2.0000000000000000134...$$

III. Observations

Observations extrapolated from the results:

- i.) $3 > R_{(a,b)} > 2$
- ii) In general, the higher the consecutive primes that undergo the formulaic consideration are, the closer R is to 2.
- iii) $R_{(5,3)}$ seems to give the highest value, i.e., 2.2(6).

§ Section 3 (Algebraic Method – Proof of interval of R)

I. Proof of minimum value of R

$$a > b$$

$$\frac{a}{b} + \frac{b}{a} > 2$$

$$a^2 + b^2 > 2ab$$

$$a^2 + b^2 - 2ab > 0$$

$$(a - b)^2 > 0 \quad \text{A}$$

II. Proof of maximum value of R

$$a > b$$

$$\frac{a}{b} + \frac{b}{a} < 3$$

$$a^2 + b^2 < 3ab$$

$$(a - b)^2 < ab$$

$$\text{let } a = b + n$$

$$(b + n - b)^2 < (b + n)b$$

$$n^2 < (b + n)b$$

$$n \cdot n < (b + n)b$$

$$n < b \Rightarrow n < b + n$$

$$0 < b \quad \text{A}$$

III. Interval of R

$$\therefore \text{(I.), (II.)} \Rightarrow R \in (2,3)$$

§ Section 4 (Conjecture)

I.

From the conducted research, we assume the following:

$$R_{(5,3)} > \equiv R_{(a,b)}$$

References note:

Original work